

Self Esteem as a Predictor of Social Maturity and Resilience among School Going Students

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ABSTRACT

This research was based on the study of relationships between self-esteem on social maturity and resilience among school going children especially adolescents (12–18-year-olds). The study helped in finding the predicting nature for self-esteem on social maturity and resilience. The tool used were Rosenberg’s Self-Esteem Scale by psychologist Morris Rosenberg, Social Maturity Scale by Dr. Nalini Rao and last Resilience Scale with 25- items by G.M Wagnild. A sample of 100 students from ages 12 to 18 years, where N = 50 for girls and N = 50 for boys were taken from Delhi-NCR region, India. The scoring was done using manuals for all the three variables respectively. The scores were analysed using Statistical method of Descriptive Analysis using SPSS version. The results showed that there were gender differences in self-esteem, social maturity, and resilience. Girls have high self-esteem, more socially maturity and were more resilient than boys. There was no significant relationship between self-esteem and social maturity. There is also no significant relationship between the self-esteem and resilience. There is a significant relationship between social maturity (personal adequacy) and resilience and self-esteem have been an interesting factor affecting social maturity of the individual and contribute to become more resilient.

Keywords:- Adolescents, Resilience, Self-Esteem and Social Maturity.

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

➤ *Self Esteem*

It basically means knowing our overall sense of worth. It also includes knowing how one is aware of their personal values, abilities, strengths, weaknesses, beliefs, ideas and how they reflect it on others. It means better understanding of our behaviors, likes, dislikes, self-respect, self-worth, and its impact on others. It also affects our relationships, physical and mental health, motivation, in fact it affects how we will behave with our surroundings. It also involves the point of view to us and for others, to help maintain the positive relations around us. It also includes knowing our strengths and limitations and hence help in breaking barriers that are present to prevent us from achieving the desired goals. To have a proper understanding on our skills, to have realistic ideology about the environment and what steps are required to maintain and improve. It also helps us to be able make choices, to have learn from previous experiences and learning to adapt to the environment. When we are aware of our overall personality, we build confidence, and always learn to improve. It also effects in the life decisions and knowing what is right and wrong and action upon it. Self-esteem also includes how well we can make decisions ourselves, how one can move on from mistakes without blaming ourselves unfairly, how to take time for ourselves to improve our habits and helps us to understand to believe that we deserve love, care, and happiness as much as others deserves. And some psychologist added as it is one's attitude towards us be it positive or negative. Self-esteem develops as we grow up and there are several factors that help in formation of self-esteem depicting high or low esteem, the situations we have gone through makes us know about ourselves, experiences that we grow through helps us to evolve and behaviors that we learnt from them forms new learning about some behavioral pattern and helps us in improving them. It also involves acceptance, which is important to move ahead in our life if anything tragic happen or even a small thing that hurt, we have acceptance we tend move on easily. That means self-acceptance is key function to our overall personality. The emotions that we face on daily purpose affects our work respectively and to not let it effect our work, that needs assurance and emotion management and when we have high self-esteem, we can easily manage emotions and hence our work. Since our learning takes place from our early years it is important to understand to learn what is best for us, and we can figure it out only when we know what our choices would be. The choice we make interpret our overall orientation towards us and our value. It allows us to make better choices.

• *Types of Self-Esteem*

There are 3 types of self-esteem that can exists in the person, and how it affects their overall self.

✓ *Low Self-Esteem*

Low self-esteem means having no confidence in themselves. It affects negatively the physical and mental health of a person. These types of people have no or low awareness how to handle themselves in positive manner. It also effects create barriers to their natural surroundings and coping from daily activities to big situations. They are more prone to loneliness, depression, and anxiety. They tend to self-doubt themselves a lot and when one self-doubts themselves every time something happens it, negatively affects them to great length and have minimal trust for their things.

✓ *High Self-Esteem*

A type of self-esteem that is high in level and that means having an overall evaluation known to them and having an optimist's attitude towards everything that is present to them. They have full awareness how they function, what are their traits, values and what kind of behaviors is appropriate to themselves and affecting positively to their surroundings. They have confidence in themselves and are able to tackle any situation that is presented to them. They have better relationships. They are able to accept and change if necessary. It is not difficult for them to handle difficult situations.

✓ *Inflated Self-Esteem*

This type of self-esteem is type of negative esteem that means people who fall under this category tend to underestimate others and thinks highly of themselves. They have confidence for themselves but no/low kindness for others. They are selfish to a extend. They may care themselves but does not give a damn what if others care.

✓ *Some other types of self-esteem existed and categorized by other psychologists are:*

- *Domain Self-esteem that states that it is related to our knowledge of self-esteem in a particular area, example- dancing.*
- *Global Self-esteem that states that it is our own overall opinion that is aggregated in nature at one each time as positive or negative in nature.*
- *State Self-esteem- states that awareness of change in social inclusion level in a particular given setting.*
- *Trait Self-esteem states that the perception of individual of their social exclusion and inclusion levels as trait nature.*
- *Stable/ true or authentic- meaning low and high self-esteem levels respectively.*

• *Factors Affecting:*

While talking about self-esteem, it comprises of several factors as well likes, self-worth, self-respect, self-improvement, etc. and all these are dependent upon the following factors-

✓ *Age*

Age is one of the main factors on which self-esteem is dependent upon. It is said to be that with age we tend to learn and change accordingly, which in hence help in developing our personality and at different age, we have different types of experiences that forms building blocks for the overall personality.

✓ *Genetics*

There are many chances that we inherit different types of traits from our parents, and it contribute to our personality. Genes play an important role in developing the personality. Sometime the traits, likes & dislikes comes from parents, and awareness of such helps in forming the good worth. Hence, genetic framework helps in shaping the individual's personality.

✓ *Past Experiences*

When we talk about what we have gone through, we tend to experience a lot of situations that we have never come across, those feelings we weren't even aware of, that mental state we never came across, but still go through to it. When we tend to come across such cases, we grow and learn. We grow from such situations to become a better person and learn to adapt to similar situation if it arrives. We are aware of the situation and hence, can make the best of our it next time. Learning through past experiences is a never-ending process and we tend to learn throughout our life.

✓ *Disability or Illness*

When we are sick, it tends to effect on our body as well as our psychological state, which in turn can affect the self-esteem and people can easily demotivate and question their worth.

✓ *Family Environment*

A family is the basics environment we grew up, all the members in the family tend to influence us in either good way or bad way. Family relations affects us very deeply and it sometimes it makes us question ourselves, our choice and even our behaviors.

✓ *Social Circumstances*

Whenever a person experience a situation that is little uncomfortable for them, that situation will help them to adapt to the it and next time, if similar situation occurs, he/she will be able to cope and handle that situation in a better manner and this will contribute to building a positive self-esteem.

✓ *Thoughts*

Positive thoughts contribute a lot in a person's life from being optimists and enabling confidence in the future work and help them to do better.

✓ *Situational Factors*

Whenever a person experience a situation that is little uncomfortable for them, that situation will help them to adapt to the it and next time, if similar situation occurs, he/she will be able to cope and handle that situation in a better manner and this will contribute to building a positive self-esteem.

• *Importance of High-Self Esteem*✓ *It boosts confidence.*✓ *It helps to know about ourselves and people around us better.*✓ *It helps to forms better decisions from small to big decisions.*✓ *It helps to form better relationships.*✓ *It helps in understanding and using the skills in better manner.*✓ *It helps the individual to cope with various activities happening around them.*✓ *It helps in knowing better ways to reduce stress only when the individual is aware of their whole personality.*✓ *It improves quality of life.*✓ *It helps to enhancing the personality.*✓ *It allows us to live our life to our full potential.*• *Theories Realated to Self-Esteem*✓ *William James Formula*

He states that self-esteem is the elementary foundation of human nature. As, it is important for our overall personality growth, it also defines our mannerism, our behavior associated and how we treat others. He stated that it is the formula included success and pretensions in it. The formation of these two elements success as how we do our work and pretensions as how we feel about ourselves, they both are interrelated and linked to each other. It may vary from person to person as we build on different hopes and expectations.

✓ *Stanley Coopersmith's Self-Esteem Theory*

He states that the formation of self-esteem happens from early childhood. The amount of care, trust, love, and security we have been given the better self-esteem would be formed. The evaluation happens from the only and grows as the factors start contributing to it, any changes in the amount provided to the child will impact the self-esteem formulation.

✓ *Morris Rosenberg Theory*

He stated that self esteem is more complicated than theory given by Coopersmith. He said that it is dependent on adolescents more than childhood or any stage of childhood. When a child compares his/her personality, choice, types of behaviors, all the daily life activities they do, when it is compared or when it is being affected by them, the self-esteem tends to begin forming. They evaluate their choices to other people of their age and hence, the self-esteem is the result of these uncertain events of the adolescence. Sometimes, along with the peer influence it is developed with parents give time and efforts to their child and how they contribute to their development.

✓ *Rosenberg's Theory*

He states that self-esteem is a subjective topic and hence is included as one of the major two components along with identity. He explains that it is largely based on one's own perceptive thoughts, feelings, and behavior. And self-esteem is made up of two further components known as Self-worth (knowing what we deserve and not taking less than that) and Efficacy (to be aware of the best results and how to proceed to it).

The children who have supportive, loving, and warm parents/caretakers tends to become more stable and mature adults whereas the children who have unsupportive, unloving, and abusive parents/caretakers tend to become less mature and unstable adults.

➤ *Social Maturity*

Social maturity is phenomenon in which an individual achieves and works on themselves for effective functioning in betterment for the society. It includes all personal attitudes, interpersonal attitudes, and the social adequacies that are need to be adapted by the individual. It also includes meaning to know what to do. It helps the individual to find appropriate role models to strive for motivation and following. It is a complex process; hence it takes a lot of time for the individual to be socially mature. Each age is different, and, at each age, one is expected to behave in a particular manner and when is behaving according to that particular manner, he/she is considered to be mature. And when these attitudes or behaviors are acting in social setting and when it not affecting others in an immature manner, the individual is said to be socially mature individual. While social maturity comes with good social development. From the beginning of the life, at each there are particular attitudes that need to be act, and when it does not happen, it hinders with the development, as slow development or inappropriate development that is not in sync with the attitudes that others kid show.

An individual who is socially matures, have the idea how to behave in certain situations in certain manner. They tend form judgments clearly and fast, they can make decisions with ease, and are able to take actions when any problem arises as soon as possible. He/she able to responsibility for their actions and try to make changes when required. They help themselves and others in need. They understand the concepts like compassion, kindness, sympathy, and empathy. They are aware of how to move ahead without creating barriers for their future self. They know how to ask for help whenever it is required. It also includes high order skills to fulfill the work and personal requirements. For functioning as healthy adults, social maturity is important for all of us. When it is not present, we tend to engage with various types of problems form tiny to huge difficulties can arise that are not only hinders with present life but for adult and future life too.

Social maturity includes the cognition development form child itself and Piaget's theory is one of the examples that explains this phenomenon. It says children have growing body and growing minds that are needed to fill with right proportion of amount of nutrients and good thoughts. Their mind development occurs from the time they conceive but, their behavioral activity for that development starts from birth. It is essential for them to learn and grow into beautiful individual physically, emotionally, and spiritually. From sensory stage that includes touch, smell, hot to move their body to vision, language and hearing development. Then, arises the complex part that includes learning, attitudes, belief formation, personality development etc. that are supposed to be working efficiently from childhood itself. When the basis for these things is form there comes the more complex process that is when the child's learning increases when they enter the school and the formation of their social development. The cognitive development occurs when given tasks are done by students with their skills and forming appropriate relationships amongst other students. The situational factors like teachers, friends, other classmates, helpers who also contribute apart from their family members affects the cognitive and social development. When they help and positively reinforce the child, the child will learn and adapt the situation in a better manner forming positive behaviors and visa versa.

The second example explaining social maturity could be the evolving self-approach. It explains social maturity as the layer formation self-approach. It tells social maturity as progressive formation that means maturity does not come in a single time experience but it forms with lots of experiences and over a long span of time. It hence also increases with age when one learns and grow to their better selves. It means understanding of social world that is complex and requires time to gain. It forms to from a

basic layer to complex layer formation. It starts with learning one thing to learning the complex things ahead. When one layer is formed the other forms when one is able to see things and recognize them appropriately not this using previous experience with better understanding. Layer by layer it forms grows endlessly. When a new perspective is given in front of the individual, how he/she takes the situation and in which manner it all comes down to how many layers have been formed and how the individual has understood the meaning of it.

There have been said that development is large process and continues to grow from babies to adults to old age. It becomes more complex, subjective, and comprehensive as we grow older. That includes 5 stages that explains this development.

- Incorporate- this is called as baby stage that includes nothing but trying to recognize the surroundings a baby can catch around them.
- Impulsive- this stage includes impulse formation and identification of the objects as their individual self like food, hunger, toys, parents face, etc.
- Imperial- till now there were only requirements for the child to fulfill, but here the child now thinks and realizes what to need and what to do when they need it. They could manipulate others to get it. This stage only focuses on what the child could need at any expense.
- Interpersonal- here, the child understands that not only him/her has the needs, but others have too. Their conscience is starting to develop.
- Institutional- the child's starts to form a self and starting to have personalized traits. They form values and learns how to do things in a particular manner. Here is the start of formation of social maturity for the child and continues to grow.

- *Kohlberg's Theory for Social Maturity*

He states that social maturity is the degree to which an individual's ability to act and respond with the situational circumstances. It includes degree of integration to one needs and purposes to social needs and requirement. He states 3 levels of moral development with 2 stages each.

- ✓ *Level -01*

Pre-conventional level- the 1st stage is called Obedience and Punishment meaning instead of focusing on punishment, one must focus on the consequences of their action and then accepting and managing it. The 2nd stage is called Individualism and Exchange meaning to do the right behavior associated to given situation and acting into the right direction rather than procrastination or distracting oneself from it.

- ✓ *Level 02*

Known as Conventional Level- this includes two stages as 3rd stage and 4th stage. The 3rd stage is called as Interpersonal relationship meaning as focusing on improving and forming better relations around us and avoiding negativity. The 4th stage is called as Authority and Social order that includes following order within the laws and maintain highest ideals for us.

- ✓ *Level 03*

Known as Post-conventional Level- this includes 5th stage as Social Contact and 6th and last stage as Universal principle. The social contact includes learning that each individual is different, and their religious beliefs are different from us and hence one should always respect and maintain boundaries so that our actions or words won't hurt them in any manner. The universal principle means developing moral principles and respecting them in every manner.

Hence, from all the above we can say social maturity is vast process and it needs to be maintained properly as each factor is individual and inter-related to one another.

Social maturity comes with social development and hence involves behavioral forms like self-confidence, leadership, kindness, compassion, sympathy, empathy, emotional regulation and adjustability, politeness and courtesy, group compatibility, fair play, dependability, cooperation skill, cheerfulness, humility, gratitude, self-awareness, and self-control.

- *Benefits of Social Maturity*

- ✓ *We can determine our own personality and other people's personality.*
- ✓ *We can regulate our behaviors and do better.*
- ✓ *We will be more confident.*
- ✓ *We will show more mature behavior.*
- ✓ *We will easily be able to communicate and express.*
- ✓ *We would always do the right thing.*
- ✓ *We would understand other's feeling with compassion, empathy, and sympathy.*
- ✓ *We would be more kind too others.*
- ✓ *We would be able to understand other actions more clearly.*

- ✓ *We will have better quality of life.*
- ✓ *We will have less expectations and more happiness around us.*
- ✓ *We would help each other rather than wasting time in jealousy or insecurity.*

- *Improving Social Maturity*

Improving social maturity must begin from childhood right from home learning to school. This includes parents, teachers' involvement to the highest level and some influence of their peers.

Some skills that need to learn from the beginning are –

- ✓ *Teaching children role of kindness and compassion.*
- ✓ *Teaching them the value of empathy and sympathy.*
- ✓ *Teaching them the importance of time.*
- ✓ *Teaching them basic manners.*
- ✓ *Good role model around them.*
- ✓ *Teaching them with little strictness and more love.*
- ✓ *Teaching them about personal hygiene.*
- ✓ *Teaching them about their personal space requirements.*
- ✓ *Teaching the hot to express themselves in presentable manner.*
- ✓ *Teaching them to pay attention to necessary things.*
- ✓ *Playing games that enhances their memory and learning.*
- ✓ *Teaching them to ask for help immediately when in trouble.*

- *Resilience*

The resilience is the capacity of the individual to adapt to situations, recover from any trauma as quickly as possible. The process where the individual overcome form existing tragedy and adapting well and work efficiently. Life is not predictable and bad things happen no matter what. There are a lot of ups and downs that can happen to anyone of us. It either can shape a person to better individuals or it can break the person. It is up to the individual's will to how well they can cope with their existing pain. How can they make their pain a tool to move ahead and do better. The change cannot happen overnight, it takes a lot of strength for the individual to move on from any tragic situation. The trauma could be death of near ones, accidents, financial and workplace stress, serious health issues etc. the rough phase is very sad, depressive, full of anxiety, and showing resistance to go back to their normal life. Adapting to situations like these is not an easy task, as much as it requires strength, will power and motivation from inside, it also requires social support as well. Having a company who is there for us, be happy in our happiness is important. Keeping people around us is important.

- *Signs Associated with Resilience-*

- ✓ *Feeling of Control*

Resilient people have high locus of control and they feel they are responsible for their actions themselves and can determine the event outcome.

- ✓ *Have Effective Emotion Regulation*

They have the tendency to manage emotions even in severe stressful conditions. It doesn't state they are not emotional people, j=they just practiced their regulation so that it does not affect them.

- ✓ *A Mentality of a Survivor*

They tend to view themselves a survivor. Even when things are hard, they move ahead with positivity and optimism.

- ✓ *Self-Compassion*

When any hard situation arises one can accept it and tends to work accordingly. Acceptance creates room for self-compassion and treat themselves with love and kindness even when situation is not in their favor.

- ✓ *Problem-Solvers*

They think practically and rationally and hence are able to find solutions to solve it and make difference to their life.

- ✓ *Social Support*

They tend to have people who constantly supports them, motivates them to do better and help in the time of crisis which is essential in the world where there is so much of negativity and disregard towards each other.

- *Elements of Resilience-*

The following are the elements described by various psychologist are-

✓ *By Susan Kobasa-*

She stated that resilience is made up of main three components as

- Challenge- Adversity is viewed as a challenge by resilient people, not as a crippling catastrophe. They see their mistakes and failures as opportunities for growth and lessons to be learned. They don't see them as a reflection of their worth or ability.
- Commitment - People that are resilient are dedicated to their lives and are ambitious, and they are very motivated to complete their purpose and not wasting their time. They are committed not only to their career, but also to their relationships, friendships, causes they care about, and religious or spiritual convictions.
- Personal control- Resilient people devote their time and energy to situations and events over which they have some influence. They feel empowered and confident because they focus on efforts that have the greatest influence. Those who spend their time worrying about uncontrollable situations may feel lost, hopeless, and powerless to do something about it.

✓ *By Martin Seligman-*

He focuses on the topics like optimism and pessimism instead of resilience even when they affect the same. He also stated three elements such as-

- Permanence- it states that people who are optimistic, who have more resilience tends to see the good outcomes as permanent solutions and bad ones as temporary.
- Pervasiveness – people who are resilience does not stop with bad situation instead they work through the bad situation and makes into the good solution one.
- Personalization- these people tend to take action to the consequences rather than blaming situation or fate and action to solve the problem and even help others to do so.

✓ *By Dr. Ginsburg-*

He explained resilience as combination of 7 integral components and they are all interrelated to each other. These seven components are called control, competence, confidence, character, coping, competence, connection, and contribution.

- Confidence - it is rooted on competence and is the belief in one's own talents. When children can demonstrate their skill in real-life settings, they build confidence. The programmed build self-confidence by finding each child's unique strengths. When the strengths of children are recognized, they soar to new heights and become self-motivated to conquer their obstacles.
- Competence- it is the ability to deal efficiently with stressful conditions. It necessitates the ability to face problems and the opportunity to practice applying such skills in dealing with stressful situations. The groups include stress-reduction and social skills training, and by acquiring these skills in a group of peers of similar ages, your child will have the opportunity to practice them and improve their proficiency.
- Character - Characteristic youngsters have a high feeling of confidence and self-worth. They are aware of their ideals and are confident in their ability to adhere to them. They can display a loving attitude toward others. They have a strong sense of right and wrong, and they are willing to make good decisions and contribute to society. Our groups strive to build character by increasing self-esteem via strengths-based work and teaching empathy and caring skills to others. Teenagers in our youth group are empowered to see that they have the potential to make decisions and that they can make "smart" decisions that lead them closer to their beliefs rather than further away from them.
- Connection- Children who have strong relationships to their peers, families, and neighborhood groups are more likely to feel secure and belong. These kids have high morals and are less prone to engage in those other damaging activities. We feel more connected in our groups, and we talk about how your kids can enhance their relationships, a compassionate member of the family, and an active part of the community.
- Control- When youngsters understand that they have power on their decisions and behaviors, they are much more likely to know to make decisions that will allow them to overcome life's obstacles. Our groups strive to give youngsters the impression that they have options in how they think and behave, and that these choices can lead to certain outcomes.
- Contribution- Children can learn the profound concept that world is a better place and they're in it if they have the chance to contribute individually to it. Hearing thanks you and expressions of gratitude when your child helps will boost their willingness to take acts and make decisions that better the world, so enhancing her personal competency, character, and deep connection. There are time in our groups for the child to consider how they may participate and make a difference in the world. We present many of ideas for projects that families can perform together to appreciate the power of participating in the parent group session.
- Coping- Children who have a diverse set of coping abilities (social skills, stress management skills) are better equipped to cope with life's obstacles and thus are better prepared to face them. The resiliency groups teach stress-reduction techniques as well as social skills for dealing with daily stresses.

- *Types of Resilience-*

- ✓ Inherent resilience- the type of resilience we are born with. It usually occurs under the seven years of age. It helps us discover the natural resilience to help in explore world and discover new things, learn a lot about new things around us and experience a lot.
- ✓ Adapted resilience- it occurs only when and trauma have been occurred. When a bad thing happens, or we experience a difficult situation adaptive resilience is learnt on the spot and can us strength to manage the stress and helps to move on.
- ✓ Learnt resilience- it is type of resilience that is learnt after a long time and with lots of past experiences. When a situation happens, we use our experience and learn from them and use the previous knowledge to overcome that trauma.
- ✓ Some other types-
- ✓ Physical resilience- Physical resilience is the ability of the body to adapt to change and recover from physical challenges, illnesses, and injuries. According to research, this form of resilience is beneficial to one's health. It has an impact on how people age, as well as how they respond to physical stress and medical concerns.
- ✓ Mental resilience- The ability to adapt to change and uncertainty is referred to as mental resilience. In times of crisis, people with this form of resilience are adaptable and calm. They use this mental toughness to solve problems, move forward, and stay optimistic in the face of adversity.
- ✓ Emotional resilience- Emotional resilience refers to the ability to control one's emotions during times of hardship. They are conscious of their emotional reactions and have a strong sense of self. They are also able to relax their minds and manage their emotions when confronted with unfavorable encounters as a result of this. When things are bad, people with this kind of perseverance may keep their spirits up. They recognize that difficulties and negative feelings are only transient and won't persist forever since they are emotionally resilient.
- ✓ Social resilience- The ability of groups to recover from harsh events is referred to as social resilience, also known as community resilience. It entails forming bonds with others and cooperating to solve problems and address issues that affect individuals individually and collectively.
- ✓ Coming together after disasters, social support, becoming aware of the community's vulnerabilities, and establishing a sense of community are all examples of social resilience. Such reactions are critical in situations where communities or large groups of people are affected, such as natural catastrophes.

- *Impact*

Resilience is the psychological power that allows humans to manage stress and adversity. It is this mental capacity provides strength that people can draw upon in times of crisis to keep them from collapsing. Dealing with loss, sad times is a part of life, and it is experienced by everyone at some point of their lives. They just differ with various degree levels. These various degree levels are called resilience. Those who have resilience tend to move on better than those who do not have resilience. They would stuck in the same loop for don't for how long, if they are not able to have resilience they will stay there. Resilience is a powerful tool to learn to make us better individuals.

- *Importance*

- ✓ *It helps in academic achievements and improved learning.*
- ✓ *Less absenteeism from work.*
- ✓ *Leads to more positive relationships.*
- ✓ *It helps to creates better resistance to cope with stress.*
- ✓ *It helps to improves emotional strength.*
- ✓ *It helps in improved lifestyle.*
- ✓ *Better control over situations.*
- ✓ *Good emotion regulation.*
- ✓ *Improved self-confidence.*
- ✓ *Less judgements.*
- ✓ *More empathetic behaviors*
- ✓ *Have positive outlook to life.*
- ✓ *Have realistic goals.*
- ✓ *Have desire to achieve those goals.*
- ✓ *Always focus on improvement.*
- ✓ *How to become more Resilient-*
- ✓ *Manage emotions and stress.*
- ✓ *Ask for help when required.*
- ✓ *Focus on what is important and working on it with consistent efforts.*
- ✓ *Convert negative thoughts into positive thoughts.*
- ✓ *Learning relaxation techniques.*
- ✓ *Practicing though awareness.*
- ✓ *Learn from past mistakes.*

- ✓ *Use experience wisely.*
- ✓ *Choose peace.*
- ✓ *Maintain perspective*
- ✓ *Developing soft skills*
- ✓ *Forming healthy relationships*
- ✓ *Be more flexible*
- ✓ *Building more confidence*
- ✓ *Setting realistic goals*

➤ *Self-Esteem and Social Maturity*

Self-esteem means having a full overall knowledge about ourselves and how it affects our surroundings. High self-esteem individuals have better relationships and low self-esteem individuals have difficult relationships. It depends individual to individual, and it takes both individuals to sit and work on that. Self-esteem is helping the individual to know about themselves and about others better. Social maturity is result of self-esteem and it helps information of behaviors that are respectfully acceptable to society. Having socially mature relationships is important part of the life and maintain them is necessary. Self esteem formation results to socially mature behavior. These behavior includes, commitment, clarity, better relationships, more goal-oriented approach, high motivation, and ultimately better quality of life from those who does not have high self esteem and are socially immature. As adolescents have exposed environment it is essential or them to be the right direction and with proper guidance, and support from others will lead to success.

➤ *Self-Esteem and Resilience*

It is said self-esteem positively influence in increasing resilience among children. While self-esteem is our own self-evaluation, it will help in finding the factors resisting to resilience and then changing and improving to those factors can lead to better resilience. Having a high self-esteem will improve the resilience. Low self-esteem will not improve the resilience and even it will create more difficulty in building resilience for the individual. It is a protective factor to resilience as it allows the individual to sit themselves and fix the situation with clarity and flexibility and in favor with others. When an individual sits themselves trying to fix the problem it increases their chances to perform better as they become more prone to environment in the manner that will benefit it rather than individuals who sit and waste and thinks the solution will come to them and they do not have to do themselves. Hence, when an individual has high self-esteem, they have high resilience.

➤ *Adolescence*

Adolescence marks from the age 10 to 19 years of age. Adolescence is age where all the types of changes occur. The physical changes include change in height and weight, hormonal changes, acute mood swings, etc. in males, change of voice, growth of facial hairs, and rapid height increase occurs. In females, facial hair growth, pubic hair growth, development of breasts, hormonal imbalances, etc. with this the emotions are heightened. Th emotional changes can be mood swings, irritability, stubbornness, bonding with others, forming relationships, gender identification, etc. this age is related to making or breaking of an individual's foundation where they learn, make, adapt, change, earn, and form. This stage of life is crucial and amongst the important of all. Here, the life choices and decisions taken are important and effects all other decisions and choice we make afterwards. Our personality is formed, we explore our choices in friends, academics, genders, career, likes and dislikes. The learning that will take place will be there present in back our brain so the learning should useful so that it can add to future work as well.

• *Two Types of Adolescence Period*

✓ *Early Adolescence*

The age category falls under this period is 10-14 years. It basically includes biological changes associated with this period varies from genetics variables and surrounding, environmental factors. Biological changes involve growth physically, like change in body structure height and weight, and development of secondary sexual organs. Here brain also undergo changes with complex processes with more physiological development. Processes also include are decision-making, risk taking and so much influence of peers.

✓ *Late Adolescence*

The age category falls under this period is 15-19 years. It includes changes such as complex processes like cognitive processes and major physical changes. The brain activity becomes more complex, and it reflects on their behavior. They become exposed to such of the world and these effects the overall development.

• *Types of Adolescence Changes*

✓ *Biological Development*

Puberty marks the adolescence stage. It includes rapid physical changes separately in girls and boys. It is the most observable stage of stage where an individual body changes and grow into mature bodily features. For girls, it includes

development of breasts, formation of pubic hairs, development of primary and secondary sex organs, marks menstruation periods, weight gain/loss, height gain, etc. for boys, it includes, change in voice modulation, growth of pubic hairs, development of primary and secondary sex organs, acute change in weight and height, etc.

✓ *Cognitive Development*

When an individual grows, their ability to think, process, reason, becomes more complex. This development involves changes in brain and its ability to develop complex skills with growth and demand and requirement of the individual. These changes have the brain increased activity and constantly learning. When we talk about cognitive processes it includes, thinking, reasoning, problems solving, creativity, speed, accuracy, attention, memory, etc. hence, maintain the cognitive development of the individual requires proper food and healthy environment.

✓ *Psychological Development*

This includes independent, freedom, body image, peer relations, identity development, family relations, academic changes, and choices, etc. this helps in formation of their life in some years later, all depends on well they are serious in learning all these skills and factors in order to become fully functional capable adult.

✓ *Moral Development*

It includes, the behaviors showing, social development, values, and beliefs. Growing up, children tend to learn what they have been taught good/ bad. This is the basic responsibility of the caretaker to impart good manners, knowledge, values, and beliefs in the child to learn. Coming to adolescence with lots of influence of peers, and parents they individual could easily distract from their already learnt morals. Hence, it is important to know what the individual is learning and influencing them into the positive direction.

• *Adolescence and Self-Esteem*

Adolescence is not an easy stage, there are constant number of changes happening simultaneously. These changes affect the daily functioning. The daily functioning forms a routine and routine forms a pattern. The pattern is helpful or not helpful is up to the individual's capacity how well they are handling with all the changes. While self-esteem starts from childhood, the childhood affects are still present and contribute to the development of self-esteem in adolescence. There are several factors affecting self-esteem and adolescence. How well the individual is adapting to their environment and how the contributing factors acting is also a major and sensitive concern for growth of the individual. Having a high self-esteem from childhood leads to better self-esteem in adolescence which is not essential, and that high self-esteem leads to growth. Having a self-esteem that is low from childhood itself, leads to imbalance self-esteem growth in adolescence, here can be 2 situations which can arise. One is continuing the same type of self-esteem to even adulthood will lead to impact negatively and everything around them. Second can be improving themselves and forming a better self-esteem resulting in growth that is helpful for future. Also, some studies showed that females have low self-esteem in adolescence than boys in adolescence. Adolescence self-esteem is something that can fluctuate from time to time. With high self esteem in childhood results in better self esteem in adulthood and children with low self-esteem from childhood itself requires more efforts and help to have better self esteem in adulthood. Individual from early adolescence to late experience change in self esteem as better. Majority adolescence have high self esteem but reminding could have low self-esteem due to many reasons like, trauma, deficiencies, or any medical grounds. So, to improve it, there is usually a group of people required to help and guide in right direction. Self-esteem has various elements inside it. From body appearance to self-worth, effectiveness, social relations, etc. hence, children spend their most time in school, so they require a group of teachers who constantly helping them in making into good and better individuals who aspire to become whatever they wish for. Even in family, efforts are needed to raise children and help them in obstacles they face with dignity and being kind to themselves without harming others in any manner. Two important relation an individual has are parent-child relation and peer relations, they need to be as positive as it can be. There should be support, love, care and no room for jealousy, insecurity, or any kind of negative emotion among them. They should grow together not make their time useless and efforts meaningless. Success will not come itself; one has to become capable of achieving it and where self-esteem lies there are better chances of it. As it also leads to acting independence, pride to their future, accepting and dealing with their consequences of actions and behaviors in responsible manner, accepting challenges and overcoming them, trying new and different things, and helping nature towards everyone. It leads to more learning and mores productivity hence, achievement.

• *Adolscence and Social Maturity*

Social maturity is essential part for the individual and society. It is an ability for the individual to behave in responsible and appropriate manner. While in this stage of age, numerous problems arise due to physical and emotional changes. There can be various conflicts with family, friends, peers, and teachers. Adjustment is also one of the main issues that can arise. Here, social development is basis for the development of social maturity concept. The child who is socially mature, he/she understands his behaviors, watch out his actions, and do things right. They can form decisions easily, forms judgements, and behaves in respectful manner that is socially acceptable. When the same child is socially immature, he/she creates conflicts with everyone around them, does not listen to anyone, become selfish, and disagrees and argues a lot. They do not have better relations with others, does a lot of mistakes, and becomes more stubborn. As adolescents have exposed environment it is essential for them to be the right direction and with proper guidance, and support from others will lead to success. As in adolescence there are several physical,

emotional, and social changes one must perform better in right direction. They change at rapid rate and the processes effects a lot of hormonal, bodily appearance changes and emotional changes, they are prone to various stimulus that eventually make or break their behavioral pattern. Evolving with good peer company is essential, as the most time of adolescence is spent with their peers and their company directly affect their development. The social circle and social media also affect and is new areas to be engage in. The way their peer company behaves they way they behave, and it might or might not be in their favor as they do not know what is right or wrong and needs guidance in the matter. So, teachers and family members are supposed to become more alert and help them. So, setting good role models is helpful, monitoring their activity (not being pushing but monitoring their behavior), encouraging them to do better and perform their tasks, exhibiting the empathetic and sympathetic behavior, building positive influence connections, teaching them self-control, managing stress in positive manner, and not indulging in harmful activities, handling pressure., setting boundaries, communicating with them, setting examples for them, and be disciplined. The emotional development also contributes to it, when individual can sit and analyze their emotions, doing positive behavioral activities, not indulging in stressful-angry situations, knowing power of being silence and saying right thing at right time only. The work life balance is not essential for adults but also for every other human being, even children and adolescence, managing time between their studies and time spending on other activities and balancing it is a form of being disciplined and one should know how to become disciplined. Learning soft skills and working towards them is effective and will help in their future projects as well. Sift skills include communication, time management, teamwork, patience, leadership, decision making and problem-solving techniques. Some other skills include like measurable activities example photoshop, education, training etc. this offers the individual to work on themselves to make them presentable and working towards their most stable behavior with high social maturity. When a person is mature socially, he/she will work in any environment with dedication and hence will succeed. Time management skills includes stress management, prioritizing, planning, organizing and goal settings. Communication skills includes written and verbal communication, presentation, constructive feedback, and active listening. Adaptability skills includes optimism, calmness, self-management, analysis, and self-motivation. Problem solving skills includes logical reasoning, decision-making, brainstorming, logical reasoning, and analysis. Teamwork skills includes coordination, collaboration, mediation, idea exchange, and resolution and conflict management. Creativity skills includes questioning, innovation, mind-mapping, experimentation, and imagination. Leadership skills includes authenticity, generosity, management skills, mentorship, and intelligence. Interpersonal skills include diplomacy, networking, empathy, tolerance, and humor. work ethic includes discipline, commitment, responsibility, dependability, and professionalism. Attention to details includes acuity, questioning, introspection, critical observation, and scheduling. Maintaining all such skills is a requirement to have become socially mature.

- *Adolescence and Resilience*

Adolescence is difficult age where an individual experience a lot of stressful events. Resilience is the ability to come back to normal after experiencing an uneasy and difficult situation. It is one of the main skills an individual should learn as early as possible because it will definitely help them to grow, and they will be able to handle future difficulties with ease. Resilient individuals tend to have better lifestyle, they can make themselves presentable in a good manner and help them to grow into a mature individual. Non-resilient individuals tend to suffer a lot until and unless they learn to cope with environment in a good manner. That is why, adolescence need to work on this skill as it is helpful for them and in future when similar situation arises, they will handle those situations better. Adolescence has a way to find out solutions because there is very creative and active at times, and they just need to use it in right ways. Those who are resilient are better able to avoid harmful and risky situations, like substance use, violence, and unwanted pregnancies, etc. they also can easily find ways to reduce stress to not letting it affect to their life, like practicing meditation, physical exercise, avoiding violence and substance abuse, etc. they have advantage over other children as they can cope up with challenges and respect responsibilities. They would have strong and healthy relationships with family members and with people other than family members. They show caring and loving behavior, supports compassion and kindness. They can manage emotions better and don't let them affect their life. They have effective approach activities leading to better learning. They make connections easily and that influence them positively. They believe in themselves and have faith in their work even when things are difficult sometimes. Parents that communicate openly with their adolescent and support their adolescent's growing independence help to boost their child's self-esteem.

- ✓ *Need for the Study*

To understand the importance of Self-esteem in the life of school going students. The place they face a lot of changes from physically (hormonal changes to body structure changes) and emotionally changes (as maturity, emotional changes, etc.). There have been a lot of times when the school going students' needs awareness about such things which are necessary for life. There is much to be faced by the adolescents in this phase even problems like loneliness, difficulty adjusting and interpersonal conflicts that can lead to severe more issues and eventually affects the individual. There is so much competition in practically everything from making friends to no wonder to where, but so much jealousy, insecurity, makes underconfident and nondependent individual and will later have damage to their life if of guiding them for the same or providing necessary help. Since it is an age where a school students often question their self-esteem, their worth and this eventually affects the social maturity (the process of developing appropriate attitudes for personal, interpersonal, and social adequacies of an individual, which are essential for functioning effectively in the Society) and Resilience (the process of adapting well in the face of adversity, trauma, tragedy, threats, or significant sources of stress) This study will be able to understand the effects of all these three variables in a school going child.

CHAPTER TWO REVIEW OF LITERATURE

➤ *Self Esteem*

• *National Studies*

Singh in 2021 conducted a study to understand the concept of psychological wellbeing relations to family relationships, self-esteem, and emotional intelligence. The sample size used was 300 adolescents as 150 girls and 150 boys. The results were calculated using descriptive analysis t test. The results showed that child's ability to grow into good individual adults requires constant care and support from the family. That eventually helps to grow emotional intelligence and self-esteem of the child and turn out to be confident adults. To improve the child's development family relations should be positive and building healthy relationships.

Das in 2020 conducted a study on role of self-esteem and emotional intelligence on the adolescents' academic achievement. The sample size includes ages 11 to 18 years. The results were calculated using T test, where standard deviation and mean were also calculated and compared with standard deviation and mean of other variables. The results showed that there is positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of adolescents and self-esteem has a positive impact on emotional intelligence which eventually have a better academic success rate.

Kumar and Jain 2020 conducted a study to understand the relationships on general wellbeing between self-esteem and self-efficacy. The sample was taken as total 400 students from 11 to 14 years of age. The calculation has been done using Anova F test and Correlation. The results showed that there has been significance effect on general wellbeing from self-esteem and self-efficacy. It positively influences the wellbeing of the adolescents.

Wagani 2019 conducted a study on role of parents individually on self-esteem of adolescence. The sample size taken was 62 students from Amity University Mumbai. Out of 62, 34 students were girls and 28 boys with nuclear families. The results were calculated using Rosenberg's self-esteem scale, Self-concept scale and Parent child relationship questionnaire. The results were calculated using bivariate correlational analysis and it showed as girls have more intimate relation with their mothers than boys have. The self-esteem with relation to parent relationship is significant and the self-esteem with relation to father have no impact on the self-esteem with mother.

Seema in 2019 conducted study on social anxiety, social competence, and self-esteem from social skills training among adolescents. The sample size taken was 200 aged 16 to 18 years old and results were calculated using T test Anova using Univariate analysis of variance. The results showed that the social skills training helps in strengthening or altering the attitudes and behaviors of the adolescents. Moreover, it also advised to add it in the curriculum to increase and improve the development.

• *International Studies*

Hu, Ling, and Huebner in 2022 conducted a study on adolescents in China as self-esteem as result of family and social support and hope. The tools used were Rosenberg's self-esteem scale, Hope scale a perceived social support scale on about 1,654 adolescents in China. The results showed it is a mediating factor that social support and family relationship have significant relationship with self-esteem and hope. A good cognitive development also has deep effect on self-esteem development in adolescence.

Du, Jian, Hua, and Qi 2021 conducted a study to study the effects of self-esteem and self-regulation with respect to positive parenting styles in Chinese adolescents. The sample taken was 11801 adolescents from 10-15 years of age. The results showed that there is significant relationship between positive parenting on self-esteem and self-regulation on children. It also states that influence is less but is present and helps to boosts confidence and self-esteem and positively affects self-regulation.

Zhao, Zheng, Pan, and Zhou 2021 conducted a study to understand the relationship between academic engagement and self-esteem in adolescents. The sample size with 418 children was selected and the mediating role of these variables had understood. The results showed that academic engagement is greater when students experience social support. It was also suggested that perceived social support, self-esteem, and academic engagement are the factors that includes in improving self-efficacy of adolescents and increasing the level of self-esteem.

Enwere, Augustine and Fidelia in 2021 conducted a study on psychological wellbeing being a predictor of self-esteem and locus of control. The sample size taken was 20,889 from Anambra state, Nigeria. The tools used were self-esteem evaluating scale, psychological wellbeing scale and locus of control scale. The data was analyzed and revealed that locus of control and self-esteem are predictors of psychological wellbeing as moderate and high respectively. It has been suggested that very school should be allotted good counsellor for linear growth for development of everyone.

Zahra, Saleem and Subhan in 2021 conducted a study on positive parenting & self-esteem with role of interpersonal skills and social comparison. The sample of 674 participants was used from Lahore, Pakistan. The parenting style questionnaire, self-esteem scale, and social comparison scale was used to research. The results showed that there is significant relationship between social comparison and interpersonal skills on positive parenting and self-esteem, but it is low. Even though it suggested to have discussion for these variables could be more elaborative in future studies.

➤ *Social Maturity*

• *National Studies*

Sam and Totuka in 2021 conducted a study on academic interests and social maturity in school going students. The research was conducted using a sample size of 60 using AI inventory for academic performance and social maturity scale. The data was analyzed using t test, standard deviations and mean for the same. The results showed that there is a gender difference on academic performance. The social maturity affects the academic interest in indirect manner.

Kaur and Kaur in 2021 conducted a study on how social maturity influences decisions making related to career. The sample of 356 students was used. The data was collected using Career decision making scale, scale for social maturity and self-efficacy scale. the data was analyzed using step wise analysis with regression. The results showed that there is a significant relationship between the social maturity and self-efficacy on career decision making.

Singh in 2020 conducted a study on social maturity and locus of control on psychological wellbeing effect on adolescents in Punjab state, India. The sample of 400 students were taken from 9th and 10th class from a government school. 200 students were males and 200 females. The sample was collected using ryff scale, and social maturity scale. the data was analyzed using stactical method with means, standard deviations and ANOVA and gender difference was also kept in mind. The results showed that there are 3 types of maturity level that affects the wellbeing of the individual. And there is a significant relationship between them.

Arora and Sharma 2018 conducted a study on school students to measure their social maturity level alongside emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing. They believed that teenagers especially should have development emotionally and needs to use emotions in a rightful manner. They took sample of 100 students from 14 to 16 years of age. They measured the social maturity using Dr. Nalini Rao's social maturity scale, emotional intelligence using emotional intelligence scale by Dr. Kaur and psychological wellbeing by Dr. Singh and Dr. Choudhary. Two-way analysis of variance was used to interpret the results. The results showed that there is significant relation between psychological wellbeing and emotional intelligence with respect to the scores obtained for the scale social maturity. It suggests that high social maturity level is associated with high wellbeing and emotional intelligence.

Joseph and Anandaraj 2017 conducted a study to find out the relationship between social maturity and self-concept of school going students. The sample taken was about 300 students from a secondary school from 3 cities Kadayannallur, Sivagiri and Sankarankovil Taluks. The tool used were Self-concept scale with 20-items by Manju Rani Aggarwal and social maturity scale of 33 items. The results were calculates using Standard Deviation, Mean, F test, and Pearson correlation method. The results showed that there is a significant relation between social maturity and self-concept among school going children and showed as moderate level.

• *International Studies*

Shokrollahzadeh, Mousavi, Zadeh, Hanis, and Araghi in 2021 conducted a study to understand the role or peer attachment in relation with social maturity and parental attachment in school going students. The sample of 3553 from age 16 to 18 years were used from Tehran. The tools that were used a s social maturity scale and parents and peers' attachment inventory. The results were calculated and analyzed using person correlational method and they showed that was a significant and non-significant cant relation both present. The significant was between parent attachment and social maturity. The non-significant was between peer attachment and social maturity.

➤ *Resilience*

• *National Studies*

Kadhiravan in 2022 conducted a study to measure resilience and academic stress in school going students. A sample of 471 students was taken from age group of 14 to 18 years from Tamil Nadu state. The results findings were that females have high resilience and better academic performance and manages stress in better manner than boys. The situational factors also affect the academic stress and performance and resilience.

Arathy in 2021 conducted a study during COVID-19 pandemic to understand how resilience and psychological distress was affecting by academic procrastination. The research was conducted on school going students age category 13 to 18 years in Kerala. The tools used were procrastination scale, resilience scale, and psychological distress scale. the results obtained showed

that there is no significant relation between resilience and academic procrastination but there is slight significant relation between psychological distress and academic procrastination.

Devi in 2021 conducted a study on adolescents' emotional health with relation to parenting style and resilience. The sample size was taken as 300 girls and 300 boys from ages 13 to 18 years from Haryana state. The tools used were Parental authority questionnaire, emotional maturity scale, state trait anger expression inventory, resiliency scale and state anxiety inventory for the sample collection. The results were calculated using SPSS version 20.0. the results showed that males have more significant relation among the variables than girls. The emotional health is greater in girls, as they tend to adapt the environment well and mature faster than boys.

Sharma and Kaur in 2021 conducted a study on positive mental health with resilience in adolescents. This study was more of theoretical research. It talked about importance of physical health and mental health simultaneously work together for an individual to work efficiently. The also talked about that how these types of pf health affects resilience process. When physical and mental health simultaneously work efficiently it increases changes of resilience level. Basically, this research was conducted to throw some light on how physical and mental health contribute in resilience.

Singh in 2020 conducted a study on emotional health of adolescence of body image emotion regulation with resilience. A sample of 600 students were taken from age category from 15 to 19 years. The scales used to collect data were Perceived stress scale, beck's depression inventory, resilience scale, career decidedness scale and emotion regulation scale. descriptive technique was used to calculate the scores and for interpretation. The results showed that females students are more on career decidedness, high appearance regulation, more resilience than boys. Whereas boys have better emotion regulation than girls.

Banerjee, Dasgupta, Paul, Suman, Burman, and Bandyopadhyay 2018 conducted a study on finding resilience level in adolescents in Kolkata, India. 151 adolescents were chosen from ages 12-14 years from Kolkata city. The CYRM-12 questionnaire is used. The results were calculated using SPSS version 16.0 and they showed that adolescents are resilient and factors affecting were class environment, parents time spending, time of activities involved, and their academic performance and girls are more resilient than boys. The children who have more positive parental relationships are more resilient to their environment and forms better understanding about everything else.

Sahdev in 2016 conducted a study on resilience affect that includes psychological, factors in Kashmiri migrants. The sample was divided into set of 3, that includes 300 in set one, 200 in set 2 and 27 in set 3. The data was collected using resilience scale of 15 items calculated by Analysis of Variance method of statistics. The results showed that females have more resilience than males and situational factors and genes have a great role to play in this. It has said to positive more in girls than boys.

- *International Studies*

Yuan in 2021 conducted a study on resilience of adolescents with training with mindfulness during COVID-19 pandemic. The sample was giving mindfulness training before filling out the resilience questionnaire and sample of 90 students was taken before and mindfulness training. The results before showed that low resilience in adolescents and after mindfulness the resilience turn out to be high. Out of 90, 84 children have change in resilience in adolescents. These changes have to stay constant, and mindfulness needs to be constant practiced in order to have good emotional intelligence and resilience.

Diaz, Fernandez, Axpe and Ferrara in 2019 conducted a study on resilience as mediating role on perceived emotional intelligence and satisfaction for life in school going students. The study was to test that if resilience is the mediator or not. The sample of 945 children was taken. The data was collected using the resilience scale, self-report questionnaire, and life satisfaction questionnaire. The results stated that the resilience is important and building resilience in teenagers is a difficult task but will power and dedication will help in building some resilience. It was also suggested that school intervention is required and helping schools students in building resilience.

Hayisama in 2018 conducted a study on resilience and social wellbeing with relation to behavioral problem in adolescents. The sample of 500 was taken between 15-18 years of age. Put of 500, 250 and 250 equally was taken for males and females. The data was collected using resilience scale and wellbeing scale by Wagnild-Young and Keyes respectively. The results were calculated using multiple regression and correlation method. The results showed that there is significant relation between behavioral pattern and resilience and wellbeing (social) and behavioral pattern with respect to gender difference that is between males and females.

Shokri and Tabrizi in 2018 conducted a study to understand the role of resilience (psychological) on perceived social support and cognitive appraisal relation with health and emotional behavior and wellbeing in adolescents. A sample of 409 boys were taken. The tools used were perceived special support, stress appraisal scale, resilience scale, lifestyle health profile scale, and PANAS scale. the results showed that psychological resilience have a mediating effect on relationship with social support and cognition appraisal alongside emotional and health behavior and wellbeing with statics of 25%, 12% and 11% in wellbeing health and behavior, positive affecting, and negative affecting respectively.

➤ *Self-Esteem and Resilience*

• *National Studies*

Kaur in 2022 conducted a study on to understand the concept of optimism in relationship with resilience, life satisfaction and self esteem in adolescence. The sample was calculated using T test, standard deviation, and mean analysis to find out the results. The results also showed gender difference in the study. The results showed majority of the sample have high optimism level and more than half have mean value for self esteem and there is a significant relation between gender difference in optimism level. And there is a positive influence of resilience and life satisfaction on the students.

• *International Studies*

Liu, Qiaolan, Jiang, Yang 2021 conducted a study on social support, resilience, and self-esteem protection against the various health problems in the age category early adolescence. The sample of data was taken as 1015 adolescents of 12.7 years of age from a school premises. The tool used were Social Support Rating scale, Block and Kremen's Ego-Resilience Scale, Rosenberg's Self-esteem scale, and Mental health inventory of middle school students. The data was calculated using bivariate partial correlations. The results showed that self-esteem positively influence resilience to work in action and have a direct effect with value of 0.279 and with opposite effect of 0.221, while it was also stated that social support in one of the many factors that contribute for the variable of mental health.

➤ *Self-Esteem, Resilience And Social Maturity*

• *International Studies*

Arslan in 2020 conducted a study on life satisfaction and social exclusion effects on resilience and self-esteem among adolescents. A sample of 1172 students was taken from a high school from classes 9th to 12th from ages 14 to 19 years. The tools used were life satisfaction scale, self-esteem scale, social maturity scale, and resilience scale. the results showed that social maturity and exclusion were directly related to self-esteem and resilience while life satisfaction is the outcome from the above relation.

CHAPTER THREE METHODOLOGY

➤ Aim:

To study the relationship between self-esteem on social maturity and resilience among school going students.

➤ Objectives:

- To study the gender differences in self-esteem, social maturity, and resilience among school students.
- To study the relationship between self-esteem and personal adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- To study the relationship between self-esteem and inter- personal adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- To study the relationship between self-esteem and social adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- To study the relationship between self-esteem and resilience among school going students.
- To study the relationship between resilience and personal adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- To study the relationship between resilience and inter- personal adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- To study the relationship between resilience and social adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- To study self-esteem as a predictor of social maturity and resilience among school going students.

➤ Hypotheses

- There is a significant gender differences in self-esteem, social maturity and resilience among school going students.
- There is a significant relationship between self-esteem and personal adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- There is a significant relationship between self-esteem and inter- personal adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- There is a significant relationship between self-esteem and social adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- There is a significant relationship between self-esteem and resilience among school students.
- There is a significant relationship between resilience and personal adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- Relationship between resilience and social adequacy for social maturity among school going students.
- Self-esteem will predict social maturity and resilience among school going students.

➤ Variables of the Study

There are 3 variables present in this study:

- Self-esteem
- Social Maturity
- Resilience

➤ Independent Variables

The independent variable in this study is Self-esteem.

➤ Dependent Variables

The dependent variable in this study is: Social Maturity and Resilience.

➤ Operational Definitions of Variables

- *Self-Esteem*- it means knowing and understanding of ourselves in the way that effects our surrounding and interaction and relations with other people around us and visa-versa.
- *Social-Maturity*- it means having a type of maturity and understanding in our social surroundings, the place we interact when we go outside.
- *Resilience*- it means how well an individual is adapting to situations that have create trauma to themselves.

➤ Sample Size

A total sample of 100 was taken, GIRLS and BOYS, where N = 50 for GIRLS and N = 50 for BOYS was taken from age 12 to 18 years of age as school going students of Delhi-NCR.

➤ *Name of Tool*

- *Rosenberg’s Self-Esteem Scale*

- ✓ *Author’s name – Morris Rosenberg*
- ✓ *Year of tool construction- 1965*
- ✓ *Scoring-*

As the RSE is a Guttman scale, scoring can be a little complicated. Scoring involves a method of combined ratings. Low self-esteem responses are “disagreed” or “strongly disagree” on items 1, 3, 4, 7, 10, and “strongly agree” or “agree” on items 2, 5, 6, 8, 9. Two or three out of three correct responses to items 3, 7, and 9 are scored as one item. One or two out of two correct responses for items 4 and 5 are considered as a single item; items 1,8, and 10 are scored as individual items; and combined correct responses (one or two out of two) to items 2 and 6 are a single item. The scale can also be scored by totalling the individual 4-point items after reverse-scoring the negatively worded items.

✓ *Reliability and Validity*

The RSE demonstrates a Guttman scale coefficient of reproducibility of .92, indicating excellent internal consistency. Test-retest reliability over a period of 2 weeks reveals correlations of .85 and .88, indicating excellent stability.

Demonstrates concurrent, predictive and construct validity using known groups. The RSE correlates significantly with other measures of self-esteem, including the Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory. In addition, the RSE correlates in the predicted direction with measures of depression and anxiety.

- *Social Maturity Scale*

- ✓ *Author’s name – Dr. Nalini Rao*
- ✓ *Year of tool construction- 2011*
- ✓ *Scoring-*

The scoring for item no. 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,18,19,20,22,23,25,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35,37,38,40, 43,44,45,46,47,48,49,53,55,58,60,61,62,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,75,76,78,79,81,82,84,85,88,89, to be score as Strongly Agree as 1, Agree as 2, Disagree as 3 and Strongly Disagree as 4.

The scoring for item no. 17,21,24,26,36,39,41,42,50,51,52,54,56,57,59,63,74,77,80,83,86,87,90 is to be scored as reverse as above, for Strongly Agree it is 4, for Agree as 3, for Disagree as 2 and for Strongly disagree as 1.

Then, adding all the scores calculated for the item no 1 to 90 as describes and Raw scores for calculated. By looking at the manual and finding z-score from raw scores to interpret the level of social maturity. The using the table for norms interpretation we can find out the Grade and Level of social maturity from raw scores.

Table 1 Social Maturity Scale

ITEM NO	SCORING
1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,18, 19,20,22,23,25,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35, 37,38,40,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,53,55,58,60, 61,62,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71,72,75,76,78, 79,81,82,84,85,88,89	Strongly Agree= 1 Agree= 2 Disagree= 3 Strongly Disagree= 4
17,21,24,26,36,39,41,42,50,51,52,54,56, 57,59,63,74,77,80,83,86,87,90	Strongly Agree= 4 Agree= 3 Disagree= 2 Strongly Disagree= 1

✓ *Reliability and Validity*

The reliability of the tool was 0.79 and the validity of the Social Maturity Scale was based on the teacher rating on the attributes of Social Maturity. The tool has been adopted according to the Indian situation for the present study. The investigator has taken the standardized tool to measure the Social Maturity of the Higher Secondary Students.

- *Resilience Scale*

- ✓ *Author’s name – G.M Wagnild*
- ✓ *Year of tool construction- 2009*

✓ *Scoring-*

The RS-14 may be a 14-item scale that measures two factors: personal competence, and acceptance of self and life. Each item is answered employing a 7-point Likert scale starting from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree', with total possible scores starting from 14 to 98. Higher scores indicate higher levels of resilience.

✓ *Reliability and Validity*

The test-retest reliability is taken form 2 years from now with the co-efficient of 0.89. the construct validity has the range of 0.92 to 0.92 and more in girls than boys.

➤ *Data Analysis / Statistical Analysis*

Descriptive and Inferential Statistics will be used to analyze the scores. Random sampling design will be used.

➤ *Ethical Considerations of the Study*

This research is only for research purposes and the confidentiality of all the subjects have been remained in tacked and will not be share to anyone else. They are strictly for used for academic purposes.

➤ *Expected Outcomes/Future Implications of the Study (How The Research Study Is Going To Benefit The Individuals, Families, Communities/ Societies, Worldwide)*

Better understanding of effect of self-esteem on social maturity and resilience among school going students and the ways to improve for the same. This research will also help in the students the importance these life skills, and for teachers to understand that each student is different and in an age like adolescence where lots of changes happen, it is important for them to guide them in right direction. For parents, to know their child better and helps them to grow into beautiful human beings they can be. In a world of constant change happening, there exists a whole world inside us which needs to be raised properly for our own sakes. To know ourselves better is good way to start how an individual will become in the future. When he/she is aware of these changes and traits, they able to make changes around and make themselves better.

CHAPTER FOUR RESULTS

This research is based on finding out the effect of self-esteem on social maturity and resilience in school going students (adolescence age). The tool used were Rosenberg’s Self-Esteem Scale by psychologist Morris Rosenberg in 1965, Social Maturity Scale by Dr. Nalini Rao invented in 2011 and last Resilience Scale with 25-items by G.M Wagnild invented in 2009. A sample of 100 students from ages 12 to 18 years were taken from Delhi-NCR region, India. The responses were collected using google forms online and were asked for consent as well. All those who agrees participated in this research. The scoring was done using manuals for all the three variables respectively. The scores were analysed using Statistical method of Descriptive Analysis using SPSS version. The following are the graphs and result table,

Fig 1 This Graph States that the Sample Size is of 100 Individuals with 50-50 Ratio of Girls and Boys

Fig 2 This graph states that the age group from 12-18 years old from Delhi-NCR region of India. The ratio for each age is for 12 years old is 13%, for 13 years old is 26%, for 14 years old is 19.3%, for 15 years old is 27.3%, for 16 years old is 13%, for 17 years old is 1.2% and for 18 years old is 0.6%.

Table 2 Standard Deviations for Each Variable

Variables	Comparisons	N	Mean	S.D.	t-test
Self esteem	Girls	50	16.12	2.6	2.596
	Boys	50	14.8	2.5	
Social maturity	Girls	50	235.9	27.02	2.067
	Boys	50	224.5	27.92	
Resilience	Girls	50	123.36	30.83	1.242
	Boys	50	115.92	29.02	

This above table describe that mean and standard deviations for each variable with their gender differences. For each variable there have been comparison between girls and boys. For self-esteem, the girls and boys have mean value of 16.12 and 14.8 respectively and standard deviation values of 2.6 and 2.5 respectively. For social maturity, the girls and boys have mean value of 235.9 and 224.5 respectively and standard deviation values of 27.02 and 27.92 respectively. For resilience, the girls and boys have mean value of 123.36 and 115.92 respectively and standard deviation values of 30.83 and 29.02 respectively. The t-test values for all each variable self-esteem, social maturity and resilience is 2.596, 2.067 and 1.242 respectively.

Fig 3 Mean and Standard Deviations

This above graph shows the mean and standard deviations for each variable with their gender differences. For each variable there have been comparison between girls and boys. For self-esteem, the girls and boys have mean value of 16.12 and 14.8 respectively and standard deviation values of 2.6 and 2.5 respectively. For social maturity, the girls and boys have mean value of 235.9 and 224.5 respectively and standard deviation values of 27.02 and 27.92 respectively. For resilience, the girls and boys have mean value of 123.36 and 115.92 respectively and standard deviation values of 30.83 and 29.02 respectively.

Table 3 Standard Deviations Values For Each Variable

Variables	Comparisons	N	Mean	S.D.	t-test
Self esteem	Girls	50	16.12	2.6	2.596
	Boys	50	14.8	2.5	
Personal Adequacy	Girls	50	73.66	12.46	1.052
	Boys	50	70.78	14.81	
Inter-personal Adequacy	Girls	50	77.54	10.44	1.537
	Boys	50	74.74	7.53	
Social Adequacy	Girls	50	84.76	10.28	2.763
	Boys	50	79.02	10.4	
Resilience	Girls	50	123.36	30.83	1.242
	Boys	50	115.92	29.02	

This above table depicts the mean and standard deviations values for each variable with their gender differences. For each variable there have been comparison between girls and boys. For self-esteem, the girls and boys have mean value of 16.12 and 14.8 respectively and standard deviation values of 2.6 and 2.5 respectively. For social maturity dimension 1 known as personal adequacy for the girls and boys have mean value of 73.66 and 70.78 respectively and standard deviation values of 12.46 and 14.81 respectively. For social maturity dimension 2 known as inter-personal adequacy for the girls and boys have mean value of 77.54 and 74.74 respectively and standard deviation values of 10.44 and 10.4 respectively. For social maturity dimension 3 known as

social adequacy for the girls and boys have mean value of 84.76 and 79.02 respectively and standard deviation values of 10.28 and 10.4 respectively. For resilience, the girls and boys have mean value of 123.36 and 115.92 respectively and standard deviation values of 30.83 and 29.02 respectively. And the t-test scores for each variable self-esteem, personal adequacy, inter-personal adequacy, social adequacy, and resilience is 2.596, 1.052, 1.537, 2,763 and 1.242 respectively.

Fig 4 Mean and Standard Deviations

This above table depicts the mean and standard deviations values for each variable with their gender differences. For each variable there have been comparison between girls and boys. For self-esteem, the girls and boys have mean value of 16.12 and 14.8 respectively and standard deviation values of 2.6 and 2.5 respectively. For social maturity dimension 1 known as personal adequacy for the girls and boys have mean value of 73.66 and 70.78 respectively and standard deviation values of 12.46 and 14.81 respectively. For social maturity dimension 2 known as inter-personal adequacy for the girls and boys have mean value of 77.54 and 74.74 respectively and standard deviation values of 10.44 and 10.4 respectively. For social maturity dimension 3 known as social adequacy for the girls and boys have mean value of 84.76 and 79.02 respectively and standard deviation values of 10.28 and 10.4 respectively. For resilience, the girls and boys have mean value of 123.36 and 115.92 respectively and standard deviation values of 30.83 and 29.02 respectively.

Table 4 Correlation between Self-Esteem and Social Maturity and Resilience

Variables	Personal adequacy D1	Inter-personal adequacy D2	Social adequacy D3	Resilience
Total Self-esteem Scores				
Pearson Correlation	.060	.039	.100	.021
Sig (2-tailed)	.551	.700	.321	.839
N	100	100	100	100

This table shows correlation with the values of variables with self-esteem and social maturity dimensions and resilience and their significant relation at any level. The r value for self-esteem and personal adequacy found to be 0.06 which is not significant at any level. The r value for self-esteem with inter-personal level is 0.039 which has no significance at any level. The r value of self-esteem in relation with social adequacy is 0.100 which has no significance at any level. The r value for self-esteem with resilience have found to be not significance at any level. Hence, this proves hypothesis no 2, 3, 4 and 5 have been rejected. The r value of resilience in relation to social maturity dimension personal adequacy is -0.230 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The r value for resilience with inter-personal level is -0.44 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The r value of resilience in relation with social adequacy is 0.074 which has no significance relation at any level.

Table 5 Correlation between Resilience and Social Maturity and Self-Esteem

Variables	Personal adequacy D1	Inter-personal adequacy D2	Social adequacy D3	Self-esteem
Resilience				
Pearson Correlation	-.230*	-0.44	.074	.021
Sig (2-tailed)	.021	.667	.463	.839
N	100	100	100	100

This above depicted the correlation between resilience and social maturity and self-esteem. Resilience and social maturity dimension personal adequacy at 0.05 level with r value of -0.230 hence no significant relationship at any level. The r value for resilience with inter-personal level is -0.44 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The r value of resilience in relation with social adequacy is 0.074 which has no significance relation at any level. Hence, this proves hypothesis no 6 and 8 have been rejected as there is no significant relationship between them. The hypothesis no 7, states that there is a significant relationship between resilience and inter-personal adequacy have found to be true and hence hypothesis is accepted.

Table 6 Correlation between Self-Esteem, Resilience, and Social Maturity

Variables	Personal adequacy D1	Inter-personal adequacy D2	Social adequacy D3
Total Self-esteem Scores			
Pearson Correlation	.060	.039	.100
Sig (2-tailed)	.551	.700	.321
N	100	100	100
Resilience			
Pearson Correlation	-.230*	-0.44	.074
Sig (2-tailed)	.021	.667	.463
N	100	100	100
Personal adequacy D1			
Pearson Correlation	1	.690**	.456
Sig (2-tailed)		.00	.000
N	100	100	100
Inter-personal adequacy D2			
Pearson Correlation	.690**	1	.433
Sig (2-tailed)	.00		.000
N	100	100	100
Social adequacy D3			
Pearson Correlation	.456	.433	1
Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
N	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

In addition to finding out the significant relationship the data have been analysed for the dimension of social maturity with dimension of social maturity along with gender differences. The r value for personal adequacy with interpersonal adequacy is 0.690 and has the significant relationship at 0.01 level. The r value for personal adequacy with social adequacy is 0.456 and has no significant relation. The r value for social adequacy with interpersonal adequacy is 0.456 and has no significant relation.

Hence, we can predict that self-esteem is a predictor for social maturity and resilience among school going students and it has been a great influence in that area. Hence the hypothesis no 9 have been accepted.

CHAPTER FIVE DISCUSSION

This research is based on the study of relationships between self-esteem on social maturity and resilience among school going children especially adolescents (12–18-year-olds). The study helps in finding the predicting nature for self-esteem on social maturity and resilience. Self-esteem basically means knowing our overall sense of worth. It also includes knowing how one is aware of their personal values, abilities, strengths, weaknesses, beliefs, ideas and how they reflect it on others. It means better understanding of our behaviours, likes, dislikes, self-respect, self-worth, and its impact on others. It also affects our relationships, physical and mental health, motivation, in fact it affects how we will behave with our surroundings. It also involves the point of view to us and for others, to help maintain the positive relations around us. It also includes knowing our strengths and limitations and hence help in breaking barriers that are present to prevent us from achieving the desired goals. To have a proper understanding on our skills, to have realistic ideology about the environment and what steps are required to maintain and improve. The children who have supportive, loving, and warm parents/caretakers tends to become more stable and mature adults whereas the children who have unsupportive, unloving, and abusive parents/caretakers tend to become less mature and unstable adults. Social maturity is phenomenon in which an individual achieves and works on themselves for effective functioning in betterment for the society. It includes all personal attitudes, interpersonal attitudes, and the social adequacies that need to be adapted by the individual. It also includes meaning to know what to do. It helps the individual to find appropriate role models to strive for motivation and following. It is a complex process; hence it takes a lot of time for the individual to be socially mature. Each age is different, and, at each age, one is expected to behave in a particular manner and when is behaving according to that particular manner, he/she is considered to be mature. And when these attitudes or behaviours are acting in social setting and when it not affecting others in an immature manner, the individual is said to be socially mature individual. Social maturity comes with social development and hence involves behavioural forms like self-confidence, leadership, kindness, compassion, sympathy, empathy, emotional regulation and adjustability, politeness and courtesy, group compatibility, fair play, dependability, cooperation skill, cheerfulness, humility, gratitude, self-awareness, and self-control. The resilience is the capacity of the individual to adapt to situations, recover from any trauma as quickly as possible. The process where the individual overcome form existing tragedy and adapting well and work efficiently. Life is not predictable and bad things happen no matter what. There are a lot of ups and downs that can happen to anyone of us. It either can shape a person to better individuals or it can break the person. It is up to the individual's will to how well they can cope with their existing pain. How can they make their pain a tool to move ahead and do better. The change cannot happen overnight, it takes a lot of strength for the individual to move on from any tragic situation. The trauma could be death of near ones, accidents, financial and workplace stress, serious health issues etc. the rough phase is very sad, depressive, full of anxiety, and showing resistance to go back to their normal life. Adapting to situations like these is not an easy task, as much as it requires strength, will power and motivation from inside, it also requires social support as well. Having a company who is there for us, be happy in our happiness is important. Keeping people around us is important. Resilience is the psychological power that allows humans to manage stress and adversity. It is this mental capacity provides strength that people can draw upon in times of crisis to keep them from collapsing. Dealing with loss, sad times is a part of life, and it is experienced by everyone at some point of their lives. They just differ with various degree levels. These various degree levels are called resilience. Those who have resilience tend to move on better than those who do not have resilience. They would stick in the same loop for don't for how long, if they are not able to have resilience they will stay there. Resilience is a powerful tool to learn to make us better individuals.

Adolescence self-esteem is something that can fluctuate from time to time. With high self-esteem in childhood results in better self-esteem in adulthood and children with low self-esteem from childhood itself requires more efforts and help to have better self-esteem in adulthood. Individual from early adolescence to late experience change in self-esteem as better. Majority adolescence have high self-esteem but remining could have low self-esteem due to many reasons like, trauma, deficiencies, or any medical grounds. So, to improve it, there is usually a group of people required to help and guide in right direction. As adolescents have exposed environment it is essential for them to be the right direction and with proper guidance, and support from others will lead to success. As in adolescence there are several physical, emotional, and social changes one must perform better in right direction. They change at rapid rate and the processes effects a lot of hormonal, bodily appearance changes and emotional changes, they are prone to various stimulus that eventually make or break their behavioural pattern. Evolving with good peer company is essential, as the most time of adolescence is spent with their peers and their company directly affect their development. The social circle and social media also affect and is new areas to be engage in. The way their peer company behaves the way they behave, and it might or might not be in their favour as they do not know what is right or wrong and needs guidance in the matter. Resilient individuals tend to have better lifestyle, they can make themselves presentable in a good manner and help them to grow into a mature individual. Non-resilient individuals tend to suffer a lot until and unless they learn to cope with environment in a good manner. That is why, adolescence need to work on this skill as it is helpful for them and in future when similar situation arises, they will handle those situations better. Adolescence has a way to find out solutions because there is very creative and active at times, and they just need to use it in right ways. Those who are resilient are better able to avoid harmful and risky situations, like substance use, violence, and unwanted pregnancies, etc. they also can easily find ways to reduce stress to not letting it affect to their life, like practicing meditation, physical exercise, avoiding violence and substance abuse, etc. they have advantage over other children as they can cope up with challenges and respect responsibilities.

The tool used were Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale by psychologist Morris Rosenberg in 1965, Social Maturity Scale by Dr. Nalini Rao invented in 2011 and last Resilience Scale with 25-items by G.M Wagnild invented in 2009. A sample of 100 students from ages 12 to 18 years, where $N = 50$ for girls and $N = 50$ for boys were taken from Delhi-NCR region, India. The responses were collected using google forms online and were asked for consent as well. All those who agrees participated in this research. The scoring was done using manuals for all the three variables respectively. The scores were analysed using Statistical method of Descriptive Analysis using SPSS version. The independent and dependent variable for the same is Self-esteem as independent and social maturity and resilience as dependent.

Table no. 4.1 and 4.2 showed that mean and standard deviations for each variable with their gender differences. For each variable there have been comparison between girls and boys. For self-esteem, the girls and boys have mean value of 16.12 and 14.8 respectively and standard deviation values of 2.6 and 2.5 respectively. This means girls tends to have more self-esteem in adolescence than boys in adolescence period. For social maturity, the girls and boys have mean value of 235.9 and 224.5 respectively and standard deviation values of 27.02 and 27.92 respectively. This states that girls have better understanding of their social environment and becomes more mature whereas it is takes to boys become mature and to gain understanding of their social environment. For social maturity dimension 1 known as personal adequacy for the girls and boys have mean value of 73.66 and 70.78 respectively and standard deviation values of 12.46 and 14.81 respectively. Hence, girls have better personal adequacy than boys. For social maturity dimension 2 known as inter-personal adequacy for the girls and boys have mean value of 77.54 and 74.74 respectively and standard deviation values of 10.44 and 10.4 respectively. Hence, girls have more knowledge of inter-personal adequacy whereas for boys it is low in comparison. For social maturity dimension 3 known as social adequacy for the girls and boys have mean value of 84.76 and 79.02 respectively and standard deviation values of 10.28 and 10.4 respectively. For dimension social adequacy girls have better social adequacy than boys. For resilience, the girls and boys have mean value of 123.36 and 115.92 respectively and standard deviation values of 30.83 and 29.02 respectively. Hence the girls are more resilient than boys. Overall, girls have high self-esteem, more socially mature and are more resilient than boys. And the t-test scores for each variable self-esteem, personal adequacy, inter-personal adequacy, social adequacy, and resilience is 2.596, 1.052, 1.537, 2.763 and 1.242 respectively.

Table no 4.3 showed the corelation with the values of variables with self-esteem and social maturity dimensions and resilience and their significant relation at any level. The r value for self-esteem and personal adequacy found to be 0.06 which is not significant at any level. The r value for self-esteem with inter-personal level is 0.039 which has no significance at any level. The r value of self-esteem in relation with social adequacy is 0.100 which has no significance at any level. The r value for self-esteem with resilience have found to be not significance at any level. Hence, this proves hypothesis no 2, 3, 4 and 5 have been rejected. The r value of resilience in relation to social maturity dimension personal adequacy is -0.230 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The r value for resilience with inter-personal level is -0.44 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The r value of resilience in relation with social adequacy is 0.074 which has no significance relation at any level.

Table no 4.4 and 4.5 showed that d the correlation between resilience and social maturity and self-esteem. Resilience and social maturity dimension personal adequacy at 0.05 level with r value of - 0.230 hence no significant relationship at any level. The r value for resilience with interpersonal level is -0.44 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The r value of resilience in relation with social adequacy is 0.074 which has no significance relation at any level. Hence, this proves hypothesis no 6 and 8 have been rejected as there is no significant relationship between them. The hypothesis no 7, states that there is a significant relationship between resilience and inter-personal adequacy have found to be true and hence hypothesis is accepted. In addition to finding out the significant relationship the data have been analysed for the dimension of social maturity with dimension of social maturity along with gender differences. The r value for personal adequacy with interpersonal adequacy is 0.690 and has the significant relationship at 0.01 level. The r value for personal adequacy with social adequacy is 0.456 and has no significant relation. The r value for social adequacy with interpersonal adequacy is 0.456 and has no significant relation.

Hence, self-esteem have been an interesting factor affecting social maturity of the individual and contribute to become more resilient and proves hypothesis no 9.

CHAPTER SIX CONCLUSION

➤ *Conclusion*

This research is based on the study of relationships between self-esteem on social maturity and resilience among school going children especially adolescents (12–18-year-olds). The study helps in finding the predicting nature for self-esteem on social maturity and resilience. The tool used were Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale by psychologist Morris Rosenberg in 1965, Social Maturity Scale by Dr. Nalini Rao invented in 2011 and last Resilience Scale with 25- items by G.M Wagnild invented in 2009. A sample of 100 students from ages 12 to 18 years, where N = 50 for girls and N = 50 for boys were taken from Delhi-NCR region, India. The responses were collected using google forms online and were asked for consent as well. All those who agrees participated in this research. The scoring was done using manuals for all the three variables respectively. The scores were analysed using Statistical method of Descriptive Analysis using SPSS version. The independent and dependent variable for the same is Self-esteem as independent and social maturity and resilience as dependent.

Based on calculations done by finding correlations of all variables and by finding mean and standard deviations vale for boys and girls same, the following are the results found out:

- The first hypothesis has been proved as there is a significant gender differences in self-esteem, social maturity and resilience among school going students. As, the mean values and standard deviations value in each variable of girls have been found more than boys.
- There is no significant relationship between self-esteem and personal adequacy, inter-personal adequacy, and social adequacy for social maturity hence hypothesis no 2, 3, and 4 have been rejected.
- There is also no significant relationship between the self-esteem and resilience and hence the hypothesis no 5 is rejected. As, there r value of self-esteem with resilience is not significant at any level of significance.
- There is a significant relationship between resilience and social maturity (inter-personal adequacy) and social adequacy is not significant at any level proving hypothesis no 6 and 8 wrong.
- The the r value of social maturity with resilience has been found significant on level 0.05 of significance. And hence, there is a significant relationship between resilience and personal adequacy proving hypothesis no 7.
- The r value of resilience in relation to social maturity dimension personal adequacy is -0.230 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. As, it is said that the personal and interpersonal adequacies help the individual to become more socially acceptable to themselves and their environment.
- And there have predictions for self-esteem to be true and influencing in social maturity and resilience proving the last hypothesis.
- Hence, self-esteem have been an interesting factor affecting social maturity of the individual and contribute to become more resilient. This states that girls have better understanding of their social environment and becomes more mature whereas it takes to boys become mature and to gain understanding of their social environment

➤ *Recommendations*

- Taking a larger sample for the study can help to replicate the results with more vulnerability and help in generalizing the results over large population.
- Conducting the study over an extensive time period can help to get better details of the cases with more valid results.

➤ *Limitations*

- The sample size could have been another limitation in the study. The research consisted of nearly 100 participants, which is a limited amount of sample.
- The study didn't involve qualitative data was collected to substantiate the data collected. The data collected was purely quantitative and hence less robust.
- The study is conducted over a limited time.

➤ *Future Implications*

- To complement this research, future research is needed that will better capture the impact of self-esteem, resilience, and social maturity on the development of the children as it lays the foundation for growth and overall personality and wellbeing.
- Further, experimental studies can be conducted to see the effect of enrichment programmes by the schools to enhance self-esteem, resilience and social maturity and their effect on one another and also in their growth and development.
- The study can be conducted on higher age group i.e., 18 years and above. This can give more clarity on enhance self-esteem, resilience, and social maturity the of this age group.

- The conduction of the study can involve a large sample from other districts and states to validate the results of the present study.

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